

MECHANICAL STABILISATION, CHEAP EFFECTIVE WAY OF IMPROVING THE MARGINAL MATERIALS FOR ROAD CONSTRUCTION

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a cost-effective method of improving the quality of marginal geo-materials through mechanical stabilisation. Two case study of the mechanical stabilisation as used during the construction of two projects in Tanzania, namely Mwika – Kilacha and Songea-Namtumbo, is presented. In both cases, substantial savings to the contract were realised. In this paper, the geotechnical and geo-mechanical properties of the geo-materials from these two cited projects before mechanical modification and after mechanical modification are presented and discussed. From the laboratory results as well as field test results, it can be concluded that mechanical stabilisation is the simplest method of stabilisation yet cost-effective means of improving the geotechnical and geo-mechanical properties of the marginal geo-materials.

Definition:

S3- Subgrade soil with CBR in the range of 3-6

G7 – Geomaterials with CBR values of not less than 7.

G15- Geomaterial with CBR values of not less than 15.

G25- natural gravel geomaterial with CBR value of not less than 25

G45- Natural gravel geomaterial with CBR values of not less than 45

CM- bound material with unconfined compressive strength of not less than 0.5 MPa.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The design of Songea – Namtumbo road project, on which the tender documents was based on included the pricing of lime stabilised improved upper subgrade layer.

The design of Marangu – Mkuu and Mwika – Kilacha road project on which the tender was based on included the pricing for cement stabilised sub-base materials of CM quality. The intent of doing lime stabilisation for the Songea – Namtumbo road project as was provided in the Material Report was to guarantee the uniformity of the road structure by stabilising the available natural geo-material using lime with two simultaneous objectives namely:

- a) To reduce the plasticity index of the naturally available geo-material to the specified maximum of 25 %. In accordance with the Materials Investigation Report, this was the primary objective of the lime stabilisation/modification.
- b) To improve the bearing capacity of the available natural gravel to achieve a CBR value of more than 15 % consistently after soaking for four days; this was the secondary objective of the lime stabilisation/modification.

For the Marangu – Mkuu and Mwika – Kilacha roads project, the intention of cement stabilisation was also to guarantee the uniformity of the road structure by stabilising the available natural volcanic materials with cement for two primary objectives:

- a) To bind the poorly graded [*gap graded*] volcanic soil into a stable and homogenous soil mass.
- b) To improve the bearing capacity of the available volcanic gravel to a CBR value of at least 45% after soaking for four days.

It is clear for both projects, that, the design engineer, during the materials investigation phase, was unable to locate a suitable geo-material to be used in the “as

dug" state. Thus, the design engineer was compelled to specify chemical [*cement or lime*] stabilisation as a means of improving the quality of geo-materials available within the project vicinity.

In this paper, a simple yet cost-effective means of improving the geotechnical and geo-mechanical properties of the geo-materials through mechanical stabilisation using natural pit-run sand as was applied for the two cited projects is presented.

2.0 PAVEMENT DESIGN

For the Namtumbo – Songea Road Project, the investigation of the material carried out by design consultant as reported in Materials Investigation Report indicated that the existing alignment soil could be classified as S3 subgrade. During pavement design, improved lower subgrade of G7 quality was provided as part of strengthening the pavement in line with the recommendation given in MoW Pavement and Material Design Manual [1999] of Tanzania. Furthermore, the investigation revealed that the material available from borrow areas which are within the project vicinity are not consistently meeting the G15 requirement for upper improved subgrade layer. Thus, it was deemed necessary by the design Engineer to opt to lime-stabilise the borrow geo-materials to reduce the plasticity index to less than the maximum specified value of 25 % and to increase the CBR value to more than minimum specified value of 15 %.

As part of the value engineering concept, a new material investigation was carried out during construction to ascertain the quality of the geo-materials available within the project vicinity. The geo-materials investigation confirmed that it was difficult to get the improved upper subgrade material of G15 quality in its "as dug" state. But through laboratory testing, it was established that the geo-materials from borrow areas could be mechanically improved by blending it with pit-run natural

sand to achieve the prerequisite requirements of G15 geo-materials as given in MoW 2000 Tanzania specifications.

For the Mwika – Kilacha road, the pavement structure was designed to carry 1-3 million equivalent standard axles. In accordance with MoW Pavement and Materials Design Manual, the pavement structure was designed with 150 mm of crushed stone CRR base and 200 mm of natural gravel subbase of G45 quality. However, due to the nature of the volcanic soil available within the project vicinity, it was challenging to get the geo-material which meets the project specification for the G45 geo-materials in its "as dug" state. The solution adopted by the Designer Engineer was to cement-stabilise the available volcanic geo-materials to improve its quality to bound materials of CM quality and use this available volcanic soil as subbase. Stabilising volcanic geo-materials using cement normally poses a problem since one of the intrinsic property of the volcanic soil is lack of clay-like materials which are required to initiate the soil-cement reaction. To improve this property, it was provided in the Materials investigation report that the volcanic soil needs to be mixed with natural soil and after that stabilised with 3-4% of cement. The amount of cement was exorbitant in particular considering the fact that 3-4% of cement was required to improve the geo-materials to achieve an unconfined compressive strength of 0.5 MPa only. For normal soils, this improvement of geo-material to get CM bound geo-materials can be achieved easily using cement content of less than 1.5% [*compare this with 3-4% of cement as was given in the contract document*].

Once again, value engineering came into play here whereby through laboratory investigation, it was established that by blending the available volcanic geo-materials with pit-run natural sand in the range 20-25%, the geotechnical, as well as the geo-mechanical properties of the volcanic geo-materials, can be improved to

meet the minimum requirements of G45 geo-materials as provided in the contract document.

4.0 BORROW AREA INVESTIGATION

For both projects, the area investigated for the borrow pits covered the entire project alignment, with the aim of locating good sand/gravel which meets at least G7 requirement for the Songea – Namtumbo project. Principally, the type of natural gravel found within the project vicinity is lateritic gravel interspersed with quartzic gravel covered with about 30-50 cm of overburden.

For the Mwika – Kilacha road, the investigation aimed at least getting the geo-materials that meets G15 or G25 requirements such that when mechanically modified, the geo-materials can meet the prerequisite of G45 geo-materials. The type of natural gravel materials found within the project vicinity was volcanic gravel interspersed with quartzitic and/or lateritic gravel, covered with about 30-50 cm of overburden. Typically, the volcanic geo-materials is associated with low density, poorly graded, cohesion-less nature and is highly porous. In most cases, in unmodified form, the volcanic soils have undesirable engineering properties in terms of pavement performance.

5.0 GEOTECHNICAL PROPERTIES OF THE BORROW MATERIALS

Several samples of geomaterial from the borrow area were gathered and tested in the laboratory for each project. The geo-material along Songea – Namtumbo project is characterised by high in-situ void ratio, which is the intrinsic nature of the geo-material available within the project vicinity due to its geological formation. The high void ratio within the soil mass is proved by the formation of gullies inside unlined ditches, making the soil within the project vicinity to be highly erodible.

For the Mwika- Kilacha road, the project soil is cohesion-less and gap graded, which is the typical characteristic property of the volcanic soil available within the project vicinity. From each borrow area, three to five samples were collected to determine the geotechnical and geo-mechanical properties of the geo-materials. For all borrow areas, the geotechnical and geo-mechanical properties of the borrow area were tested in “as dug” state and also tested after blending the borrow area geo-materials with 25% of natural pit-run sand. The tests conducted were: Particle size distribution, CBR and CBR-Swell index, Atterberg limits and MDD/OMC.

5.1 Grading

The wet sieving was carried for all soil samples collected from the borrow areas available along Songea – Namtumbo road and Mwika – Kilacha road. For the borrow samples taken from Songea- Namtumbo road, it can be seen from Figure 1 that after additional of pit-run sand, the amount passing 0.075 mm sieve was reduced and thereby improving the shear strength of the soil through improved inter-particle friction and partly due to cohesion thus leading to increase in bearing capacity of the soil.

The grading of borrow-soil samples taken from Mwika – Kilacha road indicates that is gap graded, particularly at 0.5-2 mm, which is critical particle range necessary for enhancing the compact-ability of the soil matrix, as this particle size acts as an interceptor. Owing to the fact that the soil is gap graded lacking soil particles from 0.5-2 mm and also the fine content which acts as a binder [*passing 0.075 mm*] is very low typically less than 2%, this makes the soil available along Mwika – Kilacha road to be difficult to compact. To improve this deficiency, it was imperative to blend the soil with continuously graded natural pit-run sand with sufficient fine to improve the grading. The analysis of the test results indicates that by adding about 25% of pit-run sand, the grading of the blended geo-

material was improved by transforming it from gap-graded soil to well-graded soil leading to improvement in density, compact-ability as well as bearing strength as measured using CBR.

Figure 1: grading of the borrow area geo-material before and after blending [Namtumbo – Songea Project]

Figure 2: Grading of borrow area along Mwika Kilacha road before and after blending

The grading test results before and after blending for Songea – Namtumbo and Mwika – Kilacha project is given in Figure 1 and 2, respectively.

5.2 Liquid Limit and Plasticity index

For Songea – Namtumbo road project, borrow areas geo-materials samples were

tested. The liquid limit was found to be in the range of 53-64 %. After blending with 25% of natural pit-run sand, the liquid limit was lowered from the maximum recorded of 64 % to 47%. The plasticity index was lowered to less than 25%, thus, transforming [upgrading] the G7 geo-materials to G15 compliant geo-materials.

In most cases, the volcanic soils are non-plastic; however, they have an artificially high liquid limit due to its geological formation. For the Mwika – Kilacha road, the volcanic soil was non-plastic, but the liquid limit was found to be in a range of 32–45%. After modification, the liquid limit was lowered from the recorded maximum of 45% to 34%, making it suitable to be used as G45 geo-materials. The maximum specified liquid limit for the G45 geomaterial was 40.

The summary of liquid limit and plasticity index before and after blending for the Songea – Namtumbo, and Mwika-Kilacha is shown in Figure 3 and 4, respectively.

The Atterberg limits were carried before and after blending the geo-material with 25% of pit-run sand. The Atterberg limit data of borrow geo-materials for Songea – Namtumbo are plotted in Casagrande plasticity chart and are given as Figure 5. The soil from Mwika – Kilacha is not plotted on the A-line plot because it was found to be non-plastic before and after mechanical modification. The plasticity chart indicates that the Songea – Namtumbo borrow material after and before modification are plotting just below A-line signifying that the soil is predominantly silt of high plasticity [before modification] and is transformed into the silt of low plasticity after modification [liquid limit of less than 50 %]. Based on the plasticity plot, it can further be stated that the most predominant clay mineral is likely to be kaolinite as it can be seen that before modification or even after modification, the soil is still plotting within the band of kaolinite clay.

Figure 3: Liquid limit and plasticity index before and after modification for the Songea – Namtumbo project – G7 geomaterial

Figure 4: Liquid limit before and after modification-G45 geomaterial [Mwika – Kilacha road]

5.3 California bearing ratio

The material from the investigated borrow area for the Songea – Namtumbo road project is generally of lateritic or quartzic nature with CBR consistently in excess of 15 in “as dug” state. After mechanically modifying the material, the CBR value increased, resulting in a material having CBR value of more than 20 %. The increase in CBR was due to the reduction of fine, which improved the inter-particle friction and increase in the density of soil

due to improved particle packing characteristic of the geo-materials.

Figure 5: Position of soil on plasticity chart for Namtumbo – Songea project

The geo-materials from the investigated borrow areas for Mwika - Kilacha were generally of volcanic nature, with CBR consistently in excess of 45% in its “as dug” state, while after mechanical modification using 25% natural sand, the bearing strength increased by about 30% resulting in the CBR value of more than 60.

The summary of the CBR test results before and after modifications for both cited projects are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: CBR test results before and after modification

6.0 DISCUSSION OF THE TEST RESULTS

The grading test results indicate that by blending the geo-materials with pit-run natural sand, the amount of fine [% passing 0.075 mm] in the soil was reduced for the Songea – Namtumbo geomaterial. For the Mwika – Kilacha project, the soil was lacking fines; thus, by blending with 25% of sand, the amount of fine was increased, leading to an increase in density of the soil. For the Songea - Namatumbo project, the grading was improved by reducing the excessive fines within the soil matrix, while for the Mwika – Kilacha road, the grading was improved by transforming the gap-graded soil to continuous well-graded soil with sufficient fines within the soil matrix. In both cases, the density was improved due to rearrangement of soil particle and the shear strength as measured using CBR increased due to improved inter-particle friction.

The improvement of the plasticity index of the soil for songea – Namtumbo road was due to introduction of the of the non-plastic fine which intimately mixed with plastic fines thereby changing the water retention characteristic, and physically altering the particle arrangement of the plastic fine within the soil matrix leading reduction of plasticity index.

The volcanic soil is non-plastic, but due to its geological formation, tends to exhibit a high value of the liquid limit. Introduction of the of the pit-run sand improved the particle arrangement of the fines and physical composition of the fines leading to reduction of the liquid limit.

The improvement for the CBR value of the geo-materials was due to improved inter-particle friction caused by reduction of fine for the Songea- Namtumbo road project and improvement in particle packing resulting into improved density which resulted into increase in bearing strength of the soil.

The effect of improvement in particle packing and increase in density was more marked for the volcanic soils of Mwika – Kilacha whereby the inherent characteristic of gap-graded volcanic soil was transformed to be continuous and well-graded soils leading to substantial increase in bearing capacity of the soils.

7.0 CONCLUSION

Through laboratory test results from two projects, it has been demonstrated that substantial savings can be realised to the project by using a simple but yet cost-effective method of improving the geotechnical and geo-mechanical properties of the soil by mechanical stabilisation. For the Mwika Kilacha road project, the substitution of cement stabilised subbase CM with natural gravel subbase of G45 quality resulted into a saving of 80,205,000 USD to the contract, while for Songea – Namtumbo road project, the substitution of lime stabilised upper improved subgrade [CM] with mechanically modified upper improved subgrade [G15] resulted into net savings of 1,702,350 USD to the contract.

Furthermore, by using mechanically stabilised geo-materials, placing operation can be expedited due to the fact that the placing operation is carried out in full width as opposed to chemically-stabilised geo-materials which requires 7 days curing while restricting traffic movement on top of stabilised geo-materials. Therefore, the use of mechanically stabilised geo-materials, makes the traffics accommodation within the constrained construction corridor easier and cheap leading to hassle-free traffic movement on top of the mechanically stabilised geo-materials.